

PROCESSING AND PERFORMANCE OF LINEN/HEMP FABRIC-POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Natural fibres possess relatively high specific strength and specific stiffness values. Further, the cost-effective, renewable and bio-degradable nature of the natural fibres adds to their popularity [1]. Examples of natural fibres that are currently in use include woodfibres, jute, sisal and hemp. Another fibre that might not be as popular, but useful nonetheless is linen; linen, derived from flax, is a bast fibre taken from the stalk of the plant [2].

Thermoplastic polymers offer environmental benefits, recyclability and high performance properties. As the composite industry continues to grow, it is foreseen that a shift towards thermoplastic composites will occur. Thermoplastic materials that are currently popular include polyethylene (PE), polyvinylchloride (PVC) and polypropylene (PP).

Developments in the area of natural fibre reinforced composites have focussed on short, discontinuous fibres which have a nominal length of less than 10 mm; an example would be the use of wood fibres in thermoplastics. However, long natural fibres can provide higher values of strength and stiffness to composites when compared with those provided by short discontinuous fibres. One study showed that continuous flax fibres improved the mechanical properties of composites by a factor of three when compared to those of non-woven flax fibre-reinforced composites [1].

In this study, the viability of manufacturing composite laminates by compression moulding stacks of woven linen/hemp fabrics and polypropylene sheets will be investigated. The tensile and impact properties of the resulting composite laminates will be determined. The formability of the composite laminates will then be examined using three different matched-dies with an

increasing degree of complexity, namely sinusoidal, half hexagonal and toe cap matched-dies.

2 Processing

2.1 Materials

Fibre fabrics in the form of plain-weave rolls were sourced from HempTech, Auckland [3]. Three different types of fabrics were obtained, namely 100% linen, 65% linen/35% hemp and 58% linen/42% hemp fabrics; optical micrographs of the fabrics are shown in Fig. 1. Polypropylene sheets were obtained from Field International Ltd., Auckland; the properties of the sheet are provided in Table 1 and a DSC trace of the sheet is shown in Fig. 2.

2.2 Preparation

The fabric and the polypropylene sheets were cut to the required size (280 mm x 280 mm) and weighed. A materials stack of required fibre weight fraction was arranged using a calculated number of fabric and polypropylene sheets. The warp directions of all the fabric sheets were carefully aligned in the stack. The materials stack was then placed within a mechanical spacer (290 mm x 290 mm, inside dimension) and sandwiched between two teflon coated, aluminium plates, Fig. 3.

2.3 Compression Moulding

Compression moulding was carried out in a hydraulic press, whose platens were electrically heated to 160°C. The laminate assembly, consisting of the mechanical spacer, the materials stack and the aluminium plates, was placed on the bottom platen. The top platen was moved to within a few millimetres of the laminate assembly to ensure even pre-heating. After 10 minutes, the top platen was moved down and the laminate assembly was pressed at a temperature of 160°C and a pressure of 114 kPa

for 15 minutes. The laminate assembly was then removed from the press and allowed to cool at room temperature for 10 minutes, with a cooling fan to speed up the cooling process. Lastly, the composite laminate was de-moulded from the aluminium plates. The average thickness of the laminates was 2-3 mm; the press platens were not parallel to each other and as a result laminate thickness variations of up to 15% were recorded.

3 Performance

3.1 Tensile Properties

Tensile tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D638 using three, Type I dog bone specimens, cut along the warp directions of the laminates, for each test. The tests were conducted in a universal testing machine (Instron 1185) at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min.

Any addition of fabric material significantly increases the tensile strengths and the Young's moduli of the composite laminates, Table 2; further, the tensile strengths and the Young's moduli of the composite laminates increase with increasing fibre weight fraction. The addition of hemp yarns, which are thicker and stronger than the linen yarns, increases the tensile strengths and the Young's moduli of the composites.

3.2 Impact Properties

Charpy impact tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D6110 using three notched specimens, cut along the warp directions of the laminates, for the laminates of maximum fibre weight fractions only. The tests were conducted in a pendulum impact testing machine (Ceast Resil 25) with a 1 J hammer for the 58% linen/42% hemp – polypropylene composites and 5.5 J hammer for the other composites. As the standard required test specimens with a thickness of more than 4 mm, two composite laminates each with thicknesses between 2-2.5 mm were stacked on top of one another and hot-pressed to obtain a thicker laminate.

The impact strength values for the 100% linen – polypropylene composites and the 65% linen/35% hemp – polypropylene composites are 278 J/m and 270 J/m, respectively. The much lower value of impact strength for the 58% linen/42% hemp – polypropylene composite (140.68 J/m) may be attributed to the poor quality of the hot-pressing

carried out in this case to obtain thicker laminates. Taking this fact into consideration, it can be seen that the addition of hemp yarns which are thicker, increases the impact strength of the composite laminates.

3.3 Matched-Die Forming

Matched-die forming was carried out in a hydraulic press, whose platens were first fitted with the required aluminium matched-die, Fig. 4, that had been sprayed with a release agent, teflon. The dies were then aligned as much as possible before they were bolted on to the platens, Fig. 5. The composite laminate was heated up to its forming temperature using a small conventional oven. Once the entire laminate was at a temperature of 150°C, it was quickly transferred to the middle of the bottom part of the matched-die. The top platen was then quickly lowered and the formed laminate was allowed to cool. The top platen was raised once the temperature of the moulded laminate reached 90°C; the cooling process took roughly 6 minutes before the laminate reached 90°C. In the case of the toe cap, the laminate was cut into its forming shape with a band saw, heated to the forming temperature and roughly folded to the toe cap shape before being placed into the female die for forming, Fig. 6. All the laminates were successfully moulded into the required shapes, Fig. 7; the laminates exhibited an average thickness change in the range of $\pm 5-10\%$.

4 Summary

Linen/hemp fabric composite laminates were successfully produced by compression moulding. The tensile strengths, Young's moduli and impact strengths of the composite laminates increased with increasing fibre weight fractions. All the laminates were successfully moulded using the sinusoidal, half hexagonal and the toe cap matched-dies.

References

- [1] S. Goutianos, T. Peijs, B. Nystrom and M. Skrifvars "Development of flax fibre based textile reinforcement for composite applications". *Applied Composite Materials*, Vol. 13, pp. 199-215, 2006.
- [2] G. Huang and L. Liu "Research on tensile strength of linen/polypropylene composites with various fibre volume fractions". *Materials and Design*, Vol. 29, pp. 1485-1488, 2008.
- [3] HempTech: www.hemptech.co.nz

Table 1. Properties of the polypropylene sheet

Thickness (mm)	0.6 – 0.8
Melting Point (°C)	161
Recrystallization Point (°C)	90
Density (kg/m ³)	900 – 1130
Tensile strength (MPa)	30.0 – 35.9
Young's modulus (GPa)	0.28 – 1.65
Impact strength (J/m)	140

Table 2. Properties of the linen/hemp fabric – polypropylene composite laminates

Material	Fibre weight fraction (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)
100% linen – PP composite	35	59.85	3.73
	46	69.68	6.38
	49	97.10	6.93
65% linen/35% hemp – PP composite	34	69.37	4.67
	44	78.25	5.43
58% linen/42% hemp – PP composite	32	56.34	3.83
	39	92.96	6.85

Fig 1. Optical micrographs of the fabrics: (a) the 100% linen fabric of areal density 130 g/m² (32X), (b) the 58% linen/42% hemp fabric of areal density 170 g/m² (17X), and (c) the 65% linen/35% hemp fabric of areal density 200 g/m² (17X)

Fig 2. DSC trace depicting the melting and recrystallisation temperatures of the polypropylene sheet

Fig 3. Aluminium plates and the mechanical spacer used in the manufacture of composite laminates

Fig 4. (a) The half hexagonal matched-die and (b) the sinusoidal matched-die

Fig 5. Hydraulic press used in the manufacture and forming of composite laminates

Fig 6. (a) The toe cap cut out, (b) the folded forming shape and (c) the toe cap matched-die

Fig 7. Matched-die formed shapes of linen/hemp fabric – polypropylene composite laminates: (a) the sinusoidal shape, (b) the half hexagonal shape and (c) the toe cap shape